

Acid leaching of vivianite separated from sewage sludge for recovering phosphorus and iron

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the acid leaching efficiencies of Fe and P from vivianite slurry (VS, $\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$), which is magnetically separated from anaerobic digested sludge, and elaborates on Fe and P reuse routes. The characteristics and dissolution behavior of raw VS in hydrochloric, sulfuric, phosphoric, oxalic, and citric acids are investigated. Results reveal that the primary impurities in VS are organic matter, other phosphate compounds, and Mg present in the vivianite crystal structure. Hydrochloric and sulfuric acids could effectively extract P (90%) from VS at an optimal hydrogen-to-phosphorus (H^+/P) ratio of 2.5, compared with sewage sludge ash (SSA) that normally needs an H^+/P ratio greater than 3. Hence, VS can be employed as an alternative P resource following a similar recovery route used with SSA. However, in comparison to SSA, VS use can decrease acid consumption in P extraction and the requirement for the extensive purification of cationic impurities. Furthermore, oxalic acid effectively facilitates the separation of P and Fe in VS by precipitating Fe as insoluble ferrous oxalate in acidic conditions, leading to a high Fe recovery rate of 95%. The recovery and reuse of Fe through the oxalic acid route further improves the feasibility of VS as an alternate resource.

1. Introduction

The expanding global population requires intensified crop productivity, which leads to the increasing demand for synthesizing P fertilizers from mined phosphate rock (Chen and Graedel, 2016). This demand poses a challenge for areas such as Europe that lack natural P resources because their dependence on imports makes them susceptible to geopolitical changes (Brownlie et al., 2023; Jedelhauser and Binder, 2015). Accordingly, P has been registered as a critical raw material by the European Union owing to its great importance to the economy and the extreme risks associated with its supply chain (European Commission, 2020). This situation accelerates the improvement of alternate approaches for P sourcing to obtain sustainable, stable P supply in the future.

Other than virgin rock sources, P can be recovered from several wastewater treatment effluents. Vivianite ($\text{Fe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$), which is a

dominant P form (80%–90%) in anaerobic digested sludge with sufficient Fe content (Wilfert et al., 2018), remains an underutilized, possible P feedstock with the exceptional benefit of having paramagnetic properties (Subbotnikova and Brown, 2012). This characteristic facilitates its effective magnetic separation from sewage sludge, offering an efficient procedure for P removal and recovery (Prot et al., 2019). 80% of vivianite could be recovered from sludge by employing magnetic separation, that is, over 60 % of the total P (TP) entering a municipal wastewater treatment plant could be recovered (Grönfors et al., 2019; Wijdeveld et al., 2022).

Vivianite has numerous potential applications including functioning as an Fe supplement in agriculture, a raw material of lithium iron phosphate batteries, and a source of blue pigment in paints (Prot, 2021). However, the direct application of vivianite slurry (VS) presents challenges. For example, vivianite cannot directly be used by crops needing immediate P owing to its low solubility ($K_{sp} = 10^{-36}$ at 25°C, Wu et al.,

Abbreviations: VS, Vivianite slurry; LA, Leachate acid; SSA, Sewage sludge ash; TOC, Total organic carbon; TGA, Thermogravimetric analysis; XRD, X-ray diffraction; SEM, Scanning Electron Microscopy; TEM, Transmission Electron Microscopy; EDS, Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy; SMT, Standards, Measurements and Testing; TP, Total P; OP, Organic P; NAIP, Non-apatite inorganic P; AP, Apatite P; SEDEX, Sequential extraction method.

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2019). Thus, it is a potential constituent only as slow-release P fertilizers (Samie and Römer, 2001). Moreover, the elevated Fe content considerably restricts vivianite use in agriculture and can destabilize the nutrient balance of the soil (Becker and Asch, 2005). In addition, VS can contain organic impurities or possibly toxic elements from wastewater.

Accordingly, the efficient fractionation of the Fe and P from VS and their purification are fundamental for its further use as a fertilizer and numerous other applications. However, knowledge on further processing of vivianite fractions is extremely limited. Earlier studies have used primarily alkaline treatments employing potassium hydroxide to dissolve P from VS for the preparation of liquid fertilizer (Prot et al., 2019; Santos, 2019). Acid leaching is in turn extensively employed for P extraction and traditionally applied to phosphate rocks, wastewater sludge, and P-rich ash (Fang et al., 2021), but it has not been generally utilized for vivianite leaching.

The attributes of leaching acid are crucial because they affect the efficiency of P recovery and the economic feasibility of the process. Inorganic and organic acids such as hydrochloric, sulfuric, phosphoric, oxalic, and citric acids can be employed (Fang et al., 2018; Liang et al., 2019; Reuna and Väisänen, 2018), but inorganic acids are frequently preferred because they are normally strong acids (more complete dissociation) and inexpensive. Organic acids can in turn form strong metal complexes, improving their efficiency in leaching. During acid leaching, P is dissolved to generate phosphoric acid. This crude phosphoric acid may require additional purification to eliminate metal ions, employing for example, ion exchange, organic solvent extraction, or precipitation (Biswas et al., 2009; Boniardi et al., 2021; Liang et al., 2019).

In this paper, acid leaching was examined as a pretreatment method for the recovery of Fe and P from VS. The efficiency of acid leaching with hydrochloric, sulfuric, phosphoric, oxalic, and citric acids, and the optimal conditions for maximizing P recovery were addressed. The VS was described in detail to identify the major impurities, and the influence of dissimilar leachate acid (LA) to VS ratios on the leaching of elemental P was investigated. Lastly, a precise Fe and P separation technique was constructed based on ferrous oxalate precipitation to display the viability of vivianite as a helpful resource for the recovery of P and Fe.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Separation of vivianite slurry

Vivianite slurry, with a water content of 72 ± 0.5 wt%, was acquired from the Schönebeck wastewater treatment plant (Schönebeck, Germany). The treatment adopted chemical phosphate removal technology with the utilization of ferric coagulant (Kemira PIX-111) and a pilot-scale ViviMag® technology for the magnetic separation of VS from digested sludge (Grönfors et al., 2019). The S-corrected Fe/P molar ratio, calculated as $(\text{mol Fe} - \text{mol S}) / \text{mol P}$, ranged from 0.9 to 1.2 in the anaerobic digester, accounting for sulfide precipitation of ferrous. The magnetic recovery rate of vivianite was approximately 80%. For comparison, pure vivianite was synthesized as a reference using the technique proposed by (Wang et al., 2021).

2.2. Characterization of vivianite slurry

The VS was dried by employing a vacuum freeze-dryer under dark conditions to inhibit the oxidation of ferrous species. Microwave-assisted acid digestion using nitric acid and hydrochloric acid was employed to perform liquid analyses. The elemental composition of dry VS was determined via inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (Thermo Scientific, iCAP 6500 Duo ICP-OES Spectrometer). Total organic carbon (TOC) content was quantified by employing TOC Analysis (Skalar Primacs100 analyzer). Ammonium content was established using the Spectroquant® ammonium test 1.14752.

Table 1
Sequential extraction of phosphate fractions of vivianite slurry.

Step	Extractant	Concentration (M)	P fraction names	P species	Time
1	Deionized water	-	DW-P	Soluble/weakly adsorbed P	1 h
2	Acetate buffer	0.1 (pH 5.2)	AB-P	Struvite and CaCO ₃ -P	1 h
3	Sodium hydroxide	1.0	NaOH-P	Al-P, Fe-P, organic P	16 h
4	Hydrochloric acid	1.0	HCl-P	Ca-P	16 h
5	Hydrochloric acid after calcination (450°C)	1.0	Residual P	Organic P	16 h

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of VS was conducted using a Netzsch STA 449F3 analyzer by heating the sample from 40°C to 700°C at a heating rate of 10°C/min under a nitrogen atmosphere. X-ray diffraction (XRD) assessment was completed to gauge the crystalline phases of VS using a Rigaku SmartLab 9 kW X-ray diffractometer with Co K-beta radiation. The diffraction patterns were gathered in the 2θ range from 5° to 120° at a scanning speed of 4°/min. PDXL (2nd version) software was employed to identify the phases and quantities with the Remedy Archive System File database. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was employed to examine the structural features of platinum-coated dry VS using a ZEISS Sigma HD VP instrument, operating at an acceleration voltage of 5 kV. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was performed employing JEOL JEM-2200FS with an energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) detector Ultim Max 65 to analyze the elements inside the crystal. Transmission ⁵⁷Fe Mössbauer absorption spectra were gathered at 300 K by employing a conventional constant-acceleration spectrometer using a ⁵⁷Co (Rh) source. Velocity was calibrated using an α-Fe foil. The Mössbauer spectra were fitted using Mosswin 4.0 program.

2.3. Analysis of phosphorus fractionations of vivianite slurry

The P fractions of VS were sequentially extracted following the Standards, Measurements and Testing (SMT) protocol (Pardo et al., 2003) in terms of TP, inorganic P (IP), organic P (OP), non-apatite inorganic P (NAIP, associated with Al/Fe/Mg), and apatite P (AP) fractions. In addition, a modified sequential extraction method (SEDEX; Zhang et al., 2019) was employed. Deionized water, acetate buffer, sodium hydroxide, and hydrochloric acid were used as sequential solvents with an extractant solution to the VS ratio of 50 mL/g, as shown in Table 1. Lastly, the extracted residue was separated by centrifugation at 8000 rpm, and it was washed twice with deionized water. Subsequently, the residue was vacuum-freeze dried. The dried residue was calcined at 450°C for 3 h, and then the residual P was extracted by using a hydrochloric acid solution.

2.4. Acid leaching experiments

Around 1 g of VS was mixed with 50 mL of different acid solutions (hydrochloric acid, sulfuric acid, phosphoric acid, oxalic acid, and citric acid) in a 50 mL tube. The tubes were assembled in a shaker (200 rpm), and leaching was performed at room temperature for 2 h. Next, the solutions were filtered using a 0.45 mm polyethersulfone filter, and the filtrates were gathered. For the weak acids (phosphoric acid, oxalic acid, and citric acid), the equilibrium concentration of hydrogen ions was computed using the K_a values at the solution pH of 7 to guarantee similar H⁺ concentration with strong acids (3 mmol of hydrochloric acid corresponded to 1.5 mmol of sulfuric acid, 2.17 mmol of phosphoric acid, 1.5 mmol of oxalic acid, and 1.06 mmol of citric acid, as presented in

Table 2
Elemental composition of dry vivianite slurry.

Element g/kg	Fe	P	Mg	Ca	S	Al	Na	K	NH ₄ ⁺	Total organic carbon
	210 ± 10	120 ± 10	27.5 ± 0.5	18 ± 0.1	8.4 ± 0.1	2.9 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.1	0.6 ± 0.1	5.4 ± 0.1	73.5 ± 0.5
Element mg/kg	As	Cd	Co	Cr	Cu	Hg	Mn	Ni	Pb	Zn
	<3	0.6 ± 0.1	6.1 ± 0.5	99 ± 1	140 ± 2	0.34 ± 0.1	565 ± 5	36.5 ± 1.5	10.4 ± 0.6	355 ± 5

Text S1 and Fig. S1. To explore the influence of the ratio of LA to VS (mL/g), the molar equivalent of H⁺ remained constant at 3 and 1.5 mmol/g of VS, and the acid was diluted to 5–50 mL as the LA solutions.

2.5. Analysis of iron species, phosphorus, and other elements from the leachates

Spectrophotometry was used for specific analyses of Fe and P in leachates by employing a Shimadzu UV-1800 ultraviolet-visible light spectrophotometer. The total dissolved Fe concentration was determined using Spectroquant® iron test 1.14761. The concentrations of Fe (II) and Fe(III) ions were revealed using Spectroquant® iron test 1.00796. The P concentration was measured using Spectroquant® phosphate test 1.14848. Other elemental concentrations in leachate were determined via inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (Thermo Scientific, iCAP 6500 Duo ICP-OES Spectrometer). All spectrophotometric results were obtained from each experimental condition, comprising three parallel samples, each tested only once. All ICP-OES results were derived from each condition, with two parallel samples, each tested only once. When calculating the leaching efficiencies, the leaching volume amount needs to be corrected by the water in the VS:

$$\text{Leaching efficiency} = \frac{[\text{mass (VS)} \times 0.72 + \text{LA (mL)}] \times \text{concentration (leachate)}}{\text{mass VS (g)} \times 0.28 \times \text{concentration (dry VS)}} \times 100\%$$

2.6. MINTEQ simulation

MINTEQ 3.1 was employed to simulate the equilibrium composition of solid precipitates in the presence of Fe(II), Fe(III), Ca(II), Mg(II), Al (III), ammonium, and phosphate. The original molar concentrations of the elements were calculated using the elemental concentrations of the dry VS and were modified according to a predetermined LA/VS ratio. The temperature was set to 25°C, and Cl⁻ was used to maintain charge balance. The concentration of hydrogen ions (H⁺) and counter anions

was slowly increased to mimic the influence of acid concentration on leaching. The concentrations of ions are listed in Table S1.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characteristics of vivianite slurry

3.1.1. Chemical composition

The dry VS was composed of around 13 wt% (second loss from 220°C to 700°C) of organic matter and 21 wt% (first loss from 40°C to 220°C) of crystal water, as concluded by TGA (Fig. S2). The elemental composition of dry VS reveals the predominance of P (12 wt%), Fe (21 wt%), Mg, and Ca (Table 2). Assuming that the first loss in TGA was completely ascribed to the crystal water of vivianite only, all Fe was from vivianite, or all P was from vivianite, the VS contained around 73 wt%, 62.5 wt%, and 97 wt% vivianite in dry matter, respectively. Given the identification of 13 wt% of organic matter, the vivianite content in the dry VS was approximately between 62.5 wt% and 73 wt%. In addition, the VS exhibited low concentrations of possibly toxic elements, for example, manganese (Mn), copper (Cu), nickel (Ni), arsenic (As), lead (Pb), chromium (Cr), and cadmium (Cd). According to European Union and German fertilizer regulations, all these potentially toxic elements fall below the allowable concentration limit values, as presented in Table S2.

This high purity of vivianite and low toxic element content promote using VS as a P source and minimize the requirement for additional purification.

3.1.2. Morphology and mineral composition

Organic matter co-separated with the paramagnetic vivianite by magnetic separation, as exhibited in the microscope images of the VS (Fig. 1a). Small, irregular blue particles were embedded in brown organic matter in the VS. The blue color of the vivianite demonstrated

Fig. 1. Morphology of vivianite slurry: (a) Microscopy image of vivianite slurry and (b) SEM micrograph of vivianite slurry.

Fig. 2. (a) Distributions of phosphorus species in vivianite slurry and (b) XRD patterns of the vivianite slurry and synthesized vivianite.

that part of the Fe(II) in vivianite was oxidized to Fe(III), potentially influencing its acid solubility because the ferric iron can form strengite ($\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) with phosphate, and only 10^{-4} M of strengite was dissolved at pH = 1 (Kalin et al., 2009). SEM images (Fig. 1b) reveal that the flaky crystals of vivianite aggregated into sizable spherical clusters.

The VS exhibited a TP content of 113 ± 4 mg/g of dry matter as determined by the SMT (Fig. 2a). Around 93% of the TP was inorganic, with approximately 4% HCl-P, which is frequently deemed to be apatite, while the sequential extraction revealed that 6% of the TP was AB-P which could be struvite or adsorbed P. The proportion of P species revealed that over 80% of TP was bound with Al and Fe. The principal mineral phases in the VS after drying were vivianite 97.8% ($\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and 2.2% berlinite (AlPO_4), as established by XRD (Fig. 2b). In addition, the Mössbauer spectroscopy and Fe(II)/Fe(III) measurements exhibited that over 95% of the Fe was in a ferrous form (Fig. S3). The characterization results suggested that the iron in VS is predominantly in ferrous form and present in vivianite. However, if all the iron is incorporated into vivianite, the theoretical stoichiometric

ratio of Fe and P in vivianite (1.5) implies that Fe could only bind 65% of the TP in VS.

3.1.3. Impurities of vivianite slurry

The observed deficiency in Fe content within VS can be ascribed to the impurities within the vivianite crystal structure. The structure of vivianite is built up from $(\text{Fe}^{2+})_1\text{O}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$ octahedra and $(\text{Fe}^{2+})_2\text{O}_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$ double octahedra (Rouzies et al., 1993). The ferrous of vivianite exists in three sites: one octahedral site is called site A and two equivalent octahedral sites are known as site B, obtaining a ratio of Fe^{2+} site B/ Fe^{2+} site A of 2 for pure vivianite (Prot et al., 2020, 2019). Ferrous iron in vivianite can be replaced by other divalent cations, such as Mg^{2+} and Mn^{2+} (Joëlle Kubeneck et al., 2023), and divalent cations replace preferentially site B, lowering this ratio of Fe^{2+} site B/ Fe^{2+} site A (Manning et al., 1991). By quantifying the two sites of Fe in vivianite, the VS exhibited the Fe^{2+} site B/ Fe^{2+} site A ratio of 1.4 in the Mössbauer spectroscopy (Fig. S3), which supports the presence of impurities. In addition, the TEM-EDS elemental mapping reveals that P, Fe, and Mg

Fig. 3. Leaching efficiency of vivianite as a function of H^+/P molar ratio in the presence of HCl: (a) Experimental leaching results of the key elements and trace elements and (b) MINTEQ simulation results on non-dissolved minerals and leaching of different elements.

Fig. 4. Leaching efficiency of phosphorus in SSA with different H⁺/P molar ratios (data from Table S3).

were overlappingly dispersed in the vivianite crystal (Fig. S4). The Mg content in various vivianite crystals exhibits variability, with the Mg to Fe atomic ratio ranging from 0.18 to 0.44. This implies that Mg, Fe, and P may occur in the same crystal structure. This substitution was also supported by the XRD patterns of the vivianite sample, which was dissimilar from the patterns of a database reference and the vivianite synthesized in the laboratory. Specifically, the two separated peaks of vivianite overlapped in the XRD diffractogram of the VS sample at 35° due to the impurities in the vivianite crystal structure (Egger et al., 2015).

In summary, the primary impurities in VS were organic matter, other phosphate compounds, and Mg present in the vivianite crystal structure. Although VS satisfies the legislation for agricultural applications, the extraction of Fe and P to create distinct products necessitates the removal of these impurities. Organic matter and other phosphate compounds in VS can be separated through hydrocyclone and flotation (Grönfors et al., 2019). Because Mg is part of the crystal structure, its removal necessitates the dissolution of vivianite. Acid leaching is an effective method for this purpose because it breaks down the crystal structure and releases individual elements, including Fe, P, and Mg. Subsequently, Mg and other impurities can be eliminated from the Fe- and P-rich solution.

3.2. Acid leaching of vivianite slurry

3.2.1. Vivianite slurry leaching with hydrochloric acid

The acid leaching of VS mainly entails the acid dissolution of IP minerals, as expressed in Equations 1–3. The maximum dissolution of P was attained in 15 min (Fig. S5). According to the reaction stoichiometry, three moles of H⁺ were needed to dissolve one mole of P in vivianite (Equation 1). However, the leaching experiments revealed that when the H⁺/P ratio was 2.5, the leaching efficiencies of Fe and P were approximately equal to that at a molar ratio of 3, as shown in Fig. 3a.

MINTEQ simulation also maintained that the H⁺/P molar ratio of 2 can lead to the complete dissolution of vivianite, as shown in Fig. 3b, because over 50% of the phosphate ions exist as H₂PO₄⁻ at pH of 2.3 at the end of leaching when the H⁺/P ratio was 2.5 (Fig. S1). This outcome means that the dissolution of phosphate ions needs only two H ions. Hence, the leaching of VS can preserve high efficiency while lowering the amount of acid.

In the hydrochloric acid leaching experiments (Fig. 3a), Ca exhibited an initial rise in the leaching efficiency when the H⁺/P increased, implying that the Ca compounds underwent a preferential reaction with the acid. However, no substantial leaching of P was observed, which revealed that VS contains Ca compounds such as calcium carbonate, in addition to apatite, which is more readily dissolved in acid. Then, Fe, P, Mg, and Mn demonstrated a simultaneous growth in leaching efficiency as a function of the H⁺/P ratio. Al was only observed in the leachate solution when the H⁺/P molar ratio was more than 1, which implied that Al-P needed a lower pH for dissolution compared with vivianite. MINTEQ simulation also revealed a clear sequence in mineral dissolution (Fig. 3b), with a leaching order of hydroxyapatite, vivianite, and AlPO₄, which agrees with the findings of other studies (Petzet et al., 2011; Tiwari et al., 2023). Elements that present similar dissolution patterns are usually constituents of the same structural configuration. P, Fe, Mn, and Mg exhibited parallel dissolution behaviors (Fig. 3a), which implies they coexisted within the same crystalline structure. The leaching curve of Mg intersects with those of Fe and P, indicating variability in the magnesium content across different Mg-incorporated vivianite crystals within the VS. This variability may be caused by a sequential

Fig. 5. Effect of different acids on leaching efficiencies of (a) main elements and (b) minor elements with different acids (H^+/P molar ratio of 2.5); (c) Effect of chloride ions, sulfate ions, and phosphate ions on iron and phosphorus leaching efficiency, H^+/P molar ratio = 1.

Fig. 6. Leaching efficiency of Fe and P with different H^+/P molar ratios in the presence of (a) oxalic acid and (d) citric acid; (b) distribution of ferrous species as a function of pH after addition of the oxalic acid ($[Fe^{2+}] = 0.03M$, $[PO_4^{3-}] = 0.02M$, $[Oxalate^{2-}] = 0.02M$); (c) ferrous oxalate dihydrate solubility in phosphoric acid; (e) effect of citrate on acid leaching and neutral pH citrate solution leaching; and (f) MINTEQA simulation results for different anion effects on vivianite dissolution (anion concentration = 0.02M).

dissolution, that crystals with higher Mg content dissolve first, followed by those with progressively lower Mg content.

Built on previous studies, acid consumption for SSA leaching is not as predictable as with VS likely due to the variability of phosphate species (Ca-P and Al-P) in SSA (Steckenmesser et al., 2017). In addition, other acid-reactive compounds of SSA such as calcium oxide, calcium carbonate, and magnesium oxide consume additional acid in the P extraction (Franz, 2008). Subsequently, regulating the efficiency of P release in SSA via the H^+/P molar ratio becomes more complex and less predictable (Fig. 4). Owing to the complexity of the SSA composition, the leaching efficiency of P was not clearly correlated with the P/Al ratio and P/Ca ratio (Fig. S6).

3.2.2. Effect of different acids on vivianite slurry leaching

The elemental leaching efficiencies of VS varied when using dissimilar acids (hydrochloric, sulfuric, phosphoric, oxalic, and citric acids) at a molar ratio of H^+/P of 2.5 (Figs. 5a and 5b). Hydrochloric, sulfuric, and oxalic acids exhibited a higher P leaching efficiency (approximately 90%) than phosphoric acid (60%) and citric acid (80%). The low leaching efficiency with phosphoric acid and citric acid was probably ascribed to their weak acid nature. Inorganic acids dissolve vivianite by releasing hydrogen ions, which interact with the vivianite to decompose the crystalline structure. Chloride and sulfate ions (originating from hydrochloric and sulfuric acid) did not influence Fe and P leaching efficiency, whereas the increase in concentrations of phosphate (phosphoric acid) lessened the leaching efficiencies of Fe and P (Fig. 5c). However, organic acids function through a dual mechanism when

Fig. 7. Iron and phosphorus leaching efficiency at (a) 3 mmol equilibrium concentration of hydrogen ions per gram of vivianite slurry and (b) 1.5 mmol equilibrium concentration of hydrogen ions per gram of vivianite slurry.

dissolving vivianite. Like inorganic acids, they release hydrogen ions that facilitate dissolution. Moreover, the organic anion can further react with the cations of the vivianite. Oxalic acid exhibited a low leaching efficiency for numerous elements other than P including Fe, Ca, Mg, Mn, Zn, and Ni, owing to the formation of non-soluble oxalates (Verma et al., 2019).

3.2.3. Effect of complexation and precipitation on vivianite leaching efficiency

When the H^+/P molar ratio was greater than 2, the leaching efficiency of Fe by oxalic acid decreased owing to the formation of ferrous oxalate (Fig. 6a). MINTEQ simulation revealed that ferrous oxalate possessed a low solubility in acidic environments (Fig. 6b), which facilitated the selective separation of ferrous oxalate and the dissolved P from vivianite. The solubility of ferrous oxalate in phosphoric acid solutions was only 0.044 M in a 5 M phosphoric acid, as presented in Fig. 6c. Hence, P can be separated from acid leachate of VS while precipitating and removing Fe as ferrous oxalate. Moreover, the dissolution rate of vivianite was faster than the precipitation of ferrous ions in the presence of oxalic acid (Fig. S7). This occurrence was likely because oxalic acid was first deprotonated, as shown in Equation 4, releasing hydrogen ions to dissolve vivianite at a rapid rate, as presented in Equation 1, and the subsequent reaction of oxalate ions with ferrous ions to create a precipitate at a slower rate, as expressed in Equation 5. Although complete acid leaching of VS can be reached in 15 min, the

reaction duration was extended to attain the optimal precipitation of ferrous oxalate (Fig. S7).

Citric acid exhibited superior leaching efficiency at low concentrations ($H^+/P < 2$) compared with oxalic acid, specifically for the extraction of P, whereas the leaching of Fe was less efficient (Fig. 6d). The experimental results demonstrated that citrate improved Fe and P leaching, and the sodium citrate solution caused Fe and P leaching at a pH of 7 (Fig. 6e). Previously citrate was reported to dissolve vivianite at a pH of 6 (Yang et al., 2022).

MINTEQ simulation revealed that oxalate and citrate can efficiently advance vivianite dissolution (Fig. 6f). Compared with chloride and sulfate ions, oxalate ions can increase the dissolution of vivianite by 25% at pH 4 and citrate ions by 20% at pH 5. This outcome was mainly attributed to the formation of complexes between citrate ions and divalent Fe ions. In addition, citric acid was specifically effective in leaching P from minerals that also contained Ca and Mg, such as Ca-P and Mg-P compounds, owing to its ability to form complexes with Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions (Meyer, 1974). Presumably, the Mg^{2+} chelating with citrate also improved the dissolution of Mg-type vivianite.

Fig. 8. A white precipitate formed in phosphoric acid leachate after membrane filtration: (a) SEM images and (b) EDS spectra, and phosphoric acid leaching residue (c) SEM image and (d) EDS spectra (d).

3.2.4. Effect of leachate acid to vivianite slurry ratio on vivianite leaching

The function of the leachate acid to vivianite slurry (LA/VS) ratio in the acid leaching was addressed by maintaining the dosed molarity of acids constant. With adequate acid dosing, the leaching of Fe and P was not influenced by the LA/VS ratio, except with phosphoric acid (Fig. 7a). The increase in the LA/VS ratio from 5 mL/g to 50 mL/g substantially improved P leaching from 50% to 86% with phosphorous acid. With acid dosing below a particular limit, the leaching efficiency increased with the increase of LA/VS ratio (Fig. 7b). Overall, the leaching efficiency of phosphoric acid was more sensitive to changes compared with other acids. The increase in phosphoric acid concentration lowered the concentration of free H^+ , hence preventing the vivianite dissolution, as supported by the presence of undissolved vivianite in the acid leaching residue (Fig. S8).

The increase in the liquid-to-solid ratio (L/S ratio) facilitated P leaching with SSA in several studies (Biswas et al., 2017; Ottosen et al., 2013). However, a potential decrease in P recovery with higher L/S ratios has been noted (Liang et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2018). These discrepancies may be ascribed to the complex P speciation within SSA and differences in solubility profiles under changing leaching pH. A lower L/S ratio resulted in a higher concentration of acid in contact with the material, causing a lower pH. This increased acidity can advance the dissolution of P minerals with a low solubility, such as strengite and $AlPO_4$. However, a lower L/S ratio prevents the ionization of weaker acids. This limitation could result in a decrease in the availability of H^+ ions required for enabling the binding of P to metals, thus possibly lowering the leaching efficiency. Particularly, when P is dominant as Ca-P compounds in SSA, P can be released easily and does not rely much on the pH level during acid leaching. By contrast, when P is bound to aluminum ($AlPO_4$), it has a low solubility and needs a lower pH for dissolution (Pettersson et al., 2008). The leaching efficiency of vivianite is less sensitive to the LA/VS ratio than SSA with several acids except for phosphoric acid, exhibiting a more predictable P leaching efficiency.

3.3. Strengite formation during acid leaching

When using inorganic acids to dissolve VS, a white precipitate was formed during the leaching, and it was further formed while storing the filtrate after the removal of acid leaching residue (Table S4). SEM-EDS analysis revealed that this precipitate was composed of amorphous, spherical particles with an average diameter of about 1 μm (Fig. 8a) and an Fe:P molar ratio of 1:1 (Fig. 8b and 8d). Fe existed as Fe(III) (>90% of total Fe) in the precipitate. The precipitate was also noted on the surface of the acid leaching residue (Fig. 8c). This event revealed that ferrous iron may be oxidized into ferric iron during acid leaching and can react with phosphate to form strengite. The formation of strengite was more noticeable in phosphoric acid leachates compared with other inorganic acid leachates owing to the higher pH value of the leachate (>3) and the high phosphate concentration in phosphoric acid leachate. Hence, this process reduced the leaching of Fe and P. The formation of strengite was not noted in the organic acid leachate, probably owing to the strong complexation of Fe(III) and Fe (II) with oxalate (Alnimer et al., 2023). In addition, the strong complexation of Fe(II) with citrate slowed the kinetics of Fe(II) oxidation (Krishnamurti and Huang, 1991).

3.4. Oxalate precipitate from vivianite leaching

Our experiments revealed that oxalic acid can reduce the contents of Fe, Ca, and Mg in the formed crude phosphoric acid due to precipitation with oxalate. Hence, oxalic acid could separate Fe and P in a single leaching step. The lower LA/VS ratio favored the precipitation of Ca and Mg ions, leading to the highest Ca and Mg concentration in leaching residue at the LA/VS ratio of 5 mL/g (Fig. 9a). MINTEQA simulations supported these observations, implying the formation of ferrous oxalate and calcium oxalate. Magnesium oxalate was also produced when the LA/VS was lower than 5 mL/g (Fig. 9b). However, the simulation had restrictions in accurately simulating the precipitation of ferrous oxalate.

Fig. 9. (a) Elemental distribution in oxalic acid leachate and leaching residues, (b) MINTEQ simulation of vivianite slurry leaching in the presence of 1.5 mmol oxalic acid per gram of vivianite slurry, (c) SEM image, and (d) XRD patterns of oxalic acid leaching residue.

The insoluble matter created during leaching by oxalic acid primarily consisted of hexahedron crystals (Fig. 9c). XRD analysis further confirmed that the residue contained mainly ferrous oxalate and calcium oxalate crystals (Fig. 9d). In addition, oxalic acid stimulated the precipitation of toxic metals such as Mn, Zn, Cr, Ni, Pb, Co, and Cd, decreasing their concentration in leachate compared with the leachate from hydrochloric acid treatment (Fig. S9). Consequently, oxalic acid minimized the content of divalent metal ions in the leachate, which was beneficial for selective metal recovery or treating waste streams that contain toxic metals.

3.5. Strategies for P and Fe separation

A fundamental aspect for the further valorization of VS leachate is the separation of Fe and P. Oxalic acid leaching can separate Fe and P in one step. However, the use of oxalic acid is costly, priced at US\$0.57/kg (Businessanalytiq, 2024a), which is higher than alternatives like sulfuric acid (US\$0.13/kg) (Businessanalytiq, 2024b). If only oxalic acid is employed for leaching, the organic impurities originating from VS are mixed with ferrous oxalate. Other impurities such as Ca and Mg can also be precipitated as metal oxalate compounds together with Fe to decrease the purity of ferrous oxalate. To address these challenges, VS could be leached first with phosphoric acid followed by the removal of the acid

leaching residues containing organic impurities through filtration. Increase of the concentration of phosphoric acid can enhance Fe and P leaching efficiencies, then, Fe could be removed from the leachate by precipitation as ferrous oxalate using oxalic acid. Phosphoric acid leaching produces a lower content of anionic impurities, such as chlorides and sulfates, thus reducing the need for additional purification steps. Moreover, phosphoric acid, a product of the VS leaching process, helps lower the material costs of the acid leaching process compared to other acids. The proposed route of phosphoric acid leaching followed by ferrous oxalate precipitation can remove organic impurities and reduce the Ca and Mg contents in the collected ferrous oxalate sample (Table S5). Pure ferrous oxalate can be a forerunner of lithium iron phosphate, which is an important material in the fabrication of lithium-ion batteries (Cheng et al., 2017; Churikov et al., 2014), Ferrous oxalate has a market price between US\$0.45 to US\$0.95/kg, which can offset the high cost of oxalic acid (Made-in-China, 2024). Approximately 1 kg of oxalic acid dihydrate can produce about 1.42 kg of ferrous oxalate dihydrate, showcasing a profitable conversion. Alternatively, the gathered ferrous oxalate can be dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid (Liu et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2015). Upon cooling, oxalic acid crystallizes from the solution and can be reused in the oxalate precipitation. Simultaneously, the remaining solution, enriched in Fe salts, can be employed in coagulant production, hence maximizing the material

use of the VS. This route based on phosphoric acid leaching of VS and subsequent ferrous oxalate precipitation exemplifies a comprehensive approach for the recovery and utilization of Fe and P.

Other than the oxalate route, vivianite treatment could be merged with the P recovery of SSA, such as RAVITA™ (Reuna and Väisänen, 2020), Tetraphos (Lehmkuhl and Lebek, 2019), and Rubiphos (Takhim, 2023). These technologies are constructed to recover P from SSA and recover Fe as a coagulant, employing acid leaching and the subsequent separation of the cations from the leachate to form phosphoric acid. Solvent extraction and ion exchange have been used as effective methods for eliminating metallic impurities such as Fe and Mg from phosphoric acid (Donatello and Cheeseman, 2013). The two approaches are technically feasible and have been successfully applied for commercial purposes. Similar approaches could also be tailored for the further processing of vivianite leachates. Overall, reduced acid consumption and considerable higher purity of the obtained acid leachate are remarkable benefits of using VS as a P source instead of SSA; hence, VS is a sustainable, economically attractive feedstock.

An increase in the pH of the acid leachate to precipitate calcium phosphate is also a usual phosphate recovery technique (Donatello and Cheeseman, 2013). However, the high Fe concentration in the acid leachate of VS causes the reprecipitation of vivianite at high pH (Fig. S10). Hence, VS cannot be processed with technologies such as Ash2®Phos (Cohen and Enfält, 2018), which are based on acid leaching and subsequent lime dosing.

4. Conclusion

The acid leaching of VS is depicted by a predictable acid consumption, and vivianite is completely soluble at a hydrogen-to-phosphorus (H⁺/P) molar ratio of 2.5. The acid leaching exhibits different but commonly high leaching efficiencies with numerous types of acids and is only faintly influenced by the LA/VS ratio, emphasizing its practicability in P extraction. Moreover, oxalic acid effectively extracts P and induces the separation of Fe by precipitation in the form of ferrous oxalate, facilitating the isolation of the main elements of vivianite in a one-step process.

The utilization of VS as an alternative phosphorus feedstock, compared to SSA, can provide economic and environmental benefits. The oxalic acid leaching process can recover P and produce a potential high-value by-product, ferrous oxalate. This byproduct can further be dissolved in a strong acid, allowing for the recovery and reuse of crystalline oxalic acid, while the iron-rich solution can be utilized in coagulant production. Such methods combine Fe and P recovery, offering a comprehensive approach to vivianite valorization. Additionally, VS can be combined with SSA for phosphorus recovery using established SSA processes. Compared to SSA, VS reduces acid consumption and lessens the need for extensive purification in phosphoric acid production, making it an efficient and sustainable option for P recovery.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Yudong Zhao: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Leon Korving:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Outi Grönfors:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Conceptualization. **Thomas Prot:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Terhi Suopajarvi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Tero Luukkonen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Henrikki Liimatainen:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Yudong Zhao, Outi Grönfors, Terhi Suopajarvi, Tero Luukkonen, Henrikki Liimatainen have patent METHOD FOR SEPARATING IRON AND PHOSPHORUS FROM AN IRON PHOSPHATE-BASED MATERIAL OBTAINABLE FROM A WASTE WATER TREATMENT PROCESS pending to Kemira Oyj. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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Supplementary materials

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